

Annex I

Research collaboration proposal [Part A]

Project Information

Proposal Full Title	Digitalization of informality (Acronym: DIoIN)
ERC Area(s) of the Project (max 3)	SH1_13 Labour and demographic economics; SH1_11 human resource management; SH1_10 Management; strategy; organisational behaviour
PNR priorities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ambito 1 - Salute ○ Ambito 2 - Cultura e società ○ Ambito 3 - Sicurezza ○ <u>Ambito 4 - Digitale, industria e aerospazio</u> ○ Ambito 5 - Clima ed energia ○ Ambito 6 - Cibo e ambiente
Area CUN http://www00.unibg.it/dati/bacheca/509/17601.pdf	Area 14, Sociology & Anthropology SPS/09

Applicants Information

Principal Investigator (@unibg)	Federico De Stavola
Department	Dipartimento di Lettere, Filosofia, Comunicazione
SSD	SPS/09 SOCIOLOGIA DEI PROCESSI ECONOMICI E DEL LAVORO
Research domain(s)	Labour sociology and digitalization

Please repeat the table below for each researcher

Name of the team member	Gianmarco Peterlongo
Institution/Department	Università degli Studi di Milano Dipartimento di Scienze Sociali e Politiche
SSD	SPS/09 SOCIOLOGIA DEI PROCESSI ECONOMICI E DEL LAVORO
Research domain(s)	Labour sociology and digitalization

Please fill in the table below for each researcher from foreign institution

Name of the team member	Antonio Casilli
Institution/Department	Télécom Paris
Research domain(s)	Institut polytechnique de Paris - France (EU)

Annex I

Name of the team member	Ludmila Costhek Abílio
Institution/Department	Centre of Labor Studies (CESIT)
Research domain(s)	University of Campinas (UNICAMP) - Brasil

Submit a one-page CV for **each of the researchers** that you expect to be working on the project. CVs should include details of any current and previous research and be pasted into the application, not submitted separately

Research collaboration proposal [Part B]

Abstract

ABSTRACT (max 250 words)

The DIoIN project investigates the interplay among the digital labor market, emerging technologies, and the experiences of informality in the working class of the Global South. Going beyond a localized focus, it aligns with Michael Burawoy's call for a global ethnography. The relationship between the Global South's economic periphery and the post-industrial center of the Global North doesn't follow a developmental trajectory but rather involves displacement due to neoliberal transformation and automation. Ulrich Beck suggests a "Brazilianization of Europe" rather than a "Europeanization of Brazil" in the face of new forms of work.

Digital labor and platforms play crucial roles in formalizing informality while simultaneously fostering an informalization of labor. The decline of labor guarantees from the Fordist-Keynesian era, when seen from the Global South's perspective, represents a generalization of labor conditions rather than a disruptive change. The ideology of self-entrepreneurship finds its roots in the survival strategies of the marginal pole, with platforms using digital tools and management strategies to organize crowds of formally independent workers.

The DIoIN project aims to investigate the connection between informality and the digitalization of work through research in Rio de Janeiro, using a qualitative methodology. This research focuses on the penetration of digital platforms into the informal sector, including ride-hailing and food delivery platforms. Moreover, it extends its scope to encompass digital microwork and e-commerce platforms.

1. Excellence

1.1 **State of the art and objectives (max 2.000 words)**

Please describe

- *Research areas and relevant research challenges to be investigated*
- *how your project is innovative*
- *the objectives of your project, highlighting their pertinence to real needs and to the priorities of PNR*
- *how significant the subject under investigation will be for the international scientific community and internationalisation of the Research team(s) within the Department(s)*

The DIoIN project is situated within the field of labor and organizational sociology, addressing the topic of the digitization of work and inclusivity in this sector. The topic is of strong interest in both Italy and Europe, as indicated by the National Research Program (PNR) guidelines (Area 4) and the European Research Council (ERC) guidelines (Sh1_11, 12, 13). The project aims to generate data and advancements in creating insights that may be useful for policymakers in the reduction of work marginalization and the inclusion of informal sector and vulnerable workers in the new economy permitted by Fourth Industrial Revolution. Objective 4 of the PNR is thus covered through the analysis of the impact of digitization in those economic sectors less in the spotlight of the current digital transformation, but which can play a role in renewed vitality through organizational forms, access to the labor market and value that the platform economy enables.

The uniqueness and innovation of the project are ensured by the choice of the methodological design that selects global ethnography as a perspective on the intersection between digitization and informality. This research, following Ulrich Beck's identification, explores trends in generalization in the European present by focusing on the global South and the peripheries of the world system. Here, the progressive deregulation of

Annex I

labor is generating increasingly gray areas of workers not covered by traditional social security schemes. In this way, a research on the historically disembedded labor market (in our case, the Latin American market in Brazil) is considered innovative, with the case study believed to carry a certain eloquence for the European territory.

DIOIN is based on a strong and fruitful collaboration between the University of Bergamo, represented by Federico De Stavola, the University of Milan, Gianmarco Peterlonogo, and Institut polytechnique de Paris, Antonio Casilli, who have already put forward relevant analyses on the topic with the article "Des GAFAM aux RUM: plateformes et débrouille dans le Sud global," published in the journal "Pouvoirs" in 2023. In the proposed project, collaboration extends to the University of Campinas in Brazil, with researcher Ludmila Costhek Abílio from the Center for Labor Studies contributing to greater internationalization, reaching beyond European space. The goal is to establish even more robust foundations for the research team, ensuring satisfactory results in terms of innovation and originality in the published works. This effort also serves as a basis for bringing internationalization to the partner departments, particularly to the Department of Philosophy, Letters, and Communication at the University of Bergamo.

The objective of the DIOIN project is to examine the nexus between the digital labor market, emerging digital technologies, and the experiences of informality and the marginal pole (Quijano, 1972, 1973, 1990) within the working class of the Global South. The objective surpasses a confined examination of realities solely within the Global South, resonating with Michael Burawoy's plea for a global ethnography (Burawoy, 2001)—an especially apt approach given the widespread nature of the phenomenon. In line with Burawoy's approach, we have opted to structure the project using the methodology outlined in the Extended Case Method (1998). The evolving relationship between the economic periphery of the Global South and the post-industrial center of the Global North (Mezzadra & Neilson, 2019) is not characterized by a developmental trajectory transforming the South into the North (Frank, 1978; Marini, 1981; Mezzadra & Neilson, 2013; Wallerstein, 2010), as advocated by developmentalists (Rostow, 1960). Instead, it is marked by a displacement and expulsion phenomenon (Harvey, 2003; Sassen, 2014) rooted in neoliberal transformation and automation. In the words of Ulrich Beck, the foreseeable future suggests a "Brazilianization of Europe" more than a "Europeanization of Brazil" (Beck, 2000), particularly in the context of new forms of work.

Digital labor and digital platforms act as key agents in formalizing informality while simultaneously enabling an informalization of labor (Peterlongo, 2023). The erosion of the labor guarantees typical of the Fordist-Keynesian period, when viewed from the perspective of the global South, appears more as a generalization of labor conditions than a disruptive novelty (Antunes, 2018; Mezzadra, 2021; Munck, 2013; Neffa, 2008). The ideology of self-entrepreneurship has its roots and a precedent in the self-activation and survival strategies of marginal pole (Abílio, 2019, 2020c; A. Casilli et al., 2023; De Stavola, 2022). Platforms manage to integrate and leverage these precedents, employing digital devices and management strategies to engage and lead masses of formally independent workers (De Stavola, 2020; Franco, 2021).

Moreover, the working class of the Global South is becoming an essential part of the total labor force in the development of artificial intelligence and the optimization of digital platforms (A. Casilli, 2017; Matheus et al., 2023). This dynamic fosters a utopian tech-optimism that champions philanthropic automation while concurrently obscuring the exploitation of human digital labor through international wage gaps (A. A. Casilli, 2021; Tubaro et al., 2020).

The DIOIN project seeks to explore the global phenomenon of digitizing marginal pole through an ethnographic lens focused on Brazil. The investigation aims to identify the characteristics of adverse incorporation (Phillips, 2011) in the digital economy, providing valuable data for the development of a critical analysis to enhance European inclusion policies. The focus is on leveraging the potential of the digital sector while minimizing the risks of reproducing conditions of labor precarity and social marginality.

The main hypothesis is that the penetration of digital and platform work organization in the Global South, rather than representing a novelty, retrieves pre-existing and developed objective and subjective elements in the marginal and informal sectors, subsuming them and merging with them. The analysis of the Latin American economic periphery can potentially reveal significant data that may provide insights into the reality of the center.

Brazil serves as an ideal fieldwork setting for various compelling reasons. Firstly, the extensive financialization of the informal and marginalized lower strata is conspicuous, facilitated by an array of support policies for the poor, welfare programs, and financial inclusion measures (Stolowicz W., 2016). These initiatives were initially introduced by the Cardoso government (1995-2002) and persisted under the progressive administrations of Lula (2003-2010) and Dilma (2011-2016). The financialization of lower-income strata is a precondition for the digitalization of informality. Secondly, the ongoing digitalization in informal and marginalized sectors is evident through operations like Microwork and

Annex I

- Amazon Mechanical Turk. (Grohmann et al., 2022; Grohmann & Araújo, 2021; Matheus et al., 2023). This digital transformation intersects with informal commerce and labor, creating a dynamic convergence with traditional informal labor, digital e-commerce, and platform-based employment, particularly in sectors such as food delivery and ride-hailing (Abílio, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c; Antunes & Nogueira, 2020; Vaclavik et al., 2022). Lastly, the progression of Brazilian research positions the literature as one of the most comprehensive and insightful perspectives within the Global South.
- Abílio, L. C. (2019). Uberização: Do empreendedorismo para o autogerenciamento subordinado Uberization: From entrepreneurship to subordinated self-management. *Psicoperspectivas*, 18(3), 11.
- Abílio, L. C. (2020a). Plataformas digitais e uberização: A globalização de um Sul administrado? *Revista Contracampo*, 39(1). <https://doi.org/10.22409/contracampo.v39i1.38579>
- Abílio, L. C. (2020b). Uberização e juventude periférica. *Desigualdades, autogerenciamento e novas formas de controle do trabalho. Novos Estudos - CEBRAP*, 39(3), 579–597. <https://doi.org/10.25091/s01013300202000030008>
- Abílio, L. C. (2020c). Uberização: Gerenciamento e controle do trabalhador just-in-time. In R. Antunes & A. Nogueira (A c. Di), *Uberização, trabalho digital e indústria 4.0 (1a edição)*. Boitempo.
- Antunes, R. (2018). *O privilégio da servidão: O novo proletariado de serviços na era digital*. Boitempo Editorial.
- Antunes, R., & Nogueira, A. (A c. Di). (2020). *Uberização, trabalho digital e indústria 4.0 (1a edição)*. Boitempo.
- Beck, U. (2000). *Il lavoro nell'epoca della fine del lavoro: Tramonto delle sicurezze e nuovo impegno civile*. Einaudi.
- Burawoy, M. (1998). The Extended Case Method. *Sociological Theory*, 16(1), 4–33. JSTOR.
- Burawoy, M. (2001). Manufacturing the global. *Ethnography*, 2(2), 147–159. JSTOR.
- Casilli, A. (2017). Digital Labor Studies Go Global: Toward a Digital Decolonial Turn. 21.
- Casilli, A. A. (2021). Waiting for robots: The ever-elusive myth of automation and the global exploitation of digital labor. *Sociologias*, 23(57), 112–133. <https://doi.org/10.1590/15174522-114092>
- Casilli, A., Torres-Cierpe, J., De Stavola, F., & Peterlongo, G. (2023). Des GAFAM aux RUM : plateformes et débrouille dans le Sud global. *Pouvoirs*, 185(2), 51–67. Cairn.info. <https://doi.org/10.3917/pouv.185.0051>
- De Stavola, F. (2020). Potere, controllo e soggettività nelle piattaforme digitali di food delivery: Un'analisi foucaultiana dell'app latinoamericana Rappi. *SOCIOLOGIA DEL LAVORO*, 158, 178–198. <https://doi.org/10.3280/SL2020-158009>
- De Stavola, F. (2022). *Al Sur de la plataforma: Trabajo y capital en la app latinoamericana Rappi*. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México.
- Franco, F. L. F. N. (2021). Neoliberal Platform Capitalism and Subjectivity. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 120(4), 795–808. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00382876-9443350>
- Frank, A. G. (1978). *Capitalismo y subdesarrollo en América Latina*. Siglo Veintiuno Editores.
- Grohmann, R., & Araújo, W. F. (2021). Beyond Mechanical Turk: The work of Brazilians on global AI platforms. In P. Verdegem (A c. Di), *AI for everyone: Critical perspectives* (pp. 247–266). University of Westminster Press.
- Grohmann, R., Govari Nunes, C., & Da Rosa Amaral, A. (2022). *Click Farm Platforms and informal work in Brazil (34ª ed.)*. Southern Centre for Inequality Studies. <https://doi.org/10.54223/uniwitwatersrand-10539-33453>
- Harvey, D. (2003). *The new imperialism*. Oxford University Press.
- Marini, R. M. (1981). *Dialéctica de la dependencia*. Ediciones Era.
- Matheus, V. B., Tubaro, P., & Casilli, A. A. (2023). Microwork in Brazil. Who are the workers behind artificial intelligence? DiPLab; LATRAPs.
- Mezzadra, S. (2021). Oltre il riconoscimento. Piattaforme digitali e metamorfosi del lavoro. *Filosofia politica*, 3, 487–502. <https://doi.org/10.1416/102113>
- Mezzadra, S., & Neilson, B. (2013). *Border as method, or, the multiplication of labor*. Duke University Press.
- Mezzadra, S., & Neilson, B. (2019). *The Politics of Operarion: Excavating Contemporary Capitalism*. Duke University Press.

Annex I

- Munck, R. (2013). The Precariat: A view from the South. *Third World Quarterly*, 34(5), 747–762. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2013.800751>
- Neffa, J. C. (2008). Empleo informal, trabajo no registrado, y trabajo precario: Dimensiones teóricas y conceptuales. In Sebastián. Alvarez Hayes, Agustina. Battistuzzi, Eugenio. Biaffore, A. Suárez Maestre, & J. C. Neffa, *La informalidad, la precariedad laboral y el empleo no registrado en la provincia de Buenos Aires / Ministerio de Trabajo de la provincia de Buenos Aires*.
- Peterlongo, G. (2023). Nella trama dell'algoritmo: Lavoro e circuiti informali nella gig-economy. Rosenberg & Sellier.
- Phillips, N. (2011). Informality, global production networks and the dynamics of 'adverse incorporation'. *Global Networks*, 11(3), 380–397. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0374.2011.00331.x>
- Quijano, A. (1972). La constitución del "mundo" de la marginalidad urbana. *Revista EURE - Revista de Estudios Urbanos Regionales*, 2(5), 18.
- Quijano, A. (1973). La formación de un universo marginal en las ciudades de América Latina. In M. Castells (A c. Di), *Imperialismo y urbanización en América Latina* (pp. 141–166). G. Gili.
- Quijano, A. (1990). La nueva heterogeneidad estructural de América Latina. *Revista Hueso Húmero*, 26, 8–34.
- Rostow, W. W. (1960). *The stages of growth: A non-communist manifeston*. Cambridge University Press.
- Sassen, S. (2014). *Expulsions: Brutality and complexity in the global economy*. The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Stolowicz W., B. (2016). *El misterio del posneoliberalismo (Primera edición)*. ILSA, Instituto Latinoamericano para una Sociedad y un Derecho Alternativos : Espacio Crítico Ediciones.
- Tubaro, P., Casilli, A. A., & Coville, M. (2020). The trainer, the verifier, the imitator: Three ways in which human platform workers support artificial intelligence. *Big Data & Society*, 7(1), 205395172091977. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720919776>
- Vaclavik, M. C., Oltramari, A. P. Oliveira, S. R. D. (2022). Empresariando a informalidade: Um debate teórico à luz da gig economy. *Cadernos EBAPE.BR*, 20(2), 247–258. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1679-395120210065>
- Wallerstein, I. (2010). *Alla scoperta del sistema mondo*. Manifestolibri.

1.2 Methodology (max. 1.500 words)

Please describe

- *the methodology you rely on in your project and how it makes you achieve your objectives;*
- *the interdisciplinarity of your approach, highlighting that the objectives set can only be achieved through the specific combination of knowledge and skills represented by the research group;*

In investigating the intricate relationship between informal economies and the platform economy, this research project employs the "extended case method" developed by Michael Burawoy (1998) to delve into the complexities of this relationship, with a specific focus on Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. The overarching goal is to understand how informal patterns are interwoven within the platform economy and subsequently subsumed by the overarching structures of platform companies. This project adopts a qualitative research methodology, leveraging interviews and participant observation to gain a nuanced understanding of the dynamics in the global gig economy from a perspective grounded in the Global South.

The extended case method, pioneered by Burawoy and then developed by other scholars in Economic Sociology (Van Velsen, 1979; Eliasoph & Lichterman, 1999; Wadham & Warren, 2014), is particularly apt for this research project due to its emphasis on situated knowledge, deep immersion, and continuous dialogue between theory and data – and is identifiable as part of the grounded approaches (Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Tavory & Timmermans, 2009). This method encourages researchers to engage with the broader social context and recognize the interplay between various factors shaping the phenomena under investigation. In the context of our research, the extended case method allows researchers to go beyond the immediate case and explore the broader social structures and power dynamics that influence and are influenced by informal practices. The case of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, is particularly compelling due to the city's rich history of informal economies and its rapid integration into the global digital gig economy. By employing the extended case method, the research team aims to capture not only the immediate manifestations of informality within the platform economy but also to understand the historical, cultural, and economic factors that contribute to its evolution. That of Rio de Janeiro, indeed, can be an extended case on the role of digital platforms in the highly informal urban settings of Latin American cities.

Annex I

The qualitative approach is chosen to gain in-depth insights into the lived experiences of individuals (Marzano, 2006) participating in the gig economy. This approach allows the research team to explore the complexities and nuances of informality that may not be captured by alternative methodologies. More in detail, we will employ traditional techniques of qualitative social research, such as interviews, participant observations, document analysis and online ethnography (Cardano & Gariglio, 2022).

Semi-structured interviews will be possibly conducted with various stakeholders, especially gig workers, but also platform company representatives, local policymakers, and community activists or unionists. These interviews will provide a space for participants to share their perspectives, allowing the research team to uncover the motivations, challenges, and strategies of individuals navigating the intersection of informality and the gig economy. The selection of respondents will be done through the use of platform services and also through snowball sampling from local trade union activists and/or workers.

Respondents will be selected from workers across various sectors of the digital platforms economy to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between digitization and informality. We will conduct interviews with Uber Moto drivers, a service already informally present in some peripheral areas of major Brazilian cities. Unlike car drivers, these individuals enter the labor market with a lower initial investment, suggesting a strong connection between digitization and the marginal sector, as well as their propensity to adapt and make do.

Interviews will also be conducted with workers from Microworker and Appen, two platforms specializing in microtasks and digital labor. Their concentration in the city of Rio de Janeiro ranks second in the country, after São Paulo and before Belo Horizonte (Matheus et al., 2023). These platforms play a crucial role in supporting the development of Artificial Intelligence and are intricately intertwined with the life stories of favelas and marginalized neighborhoods, involving other informal practices geared towards survival.

Lastly, we will delve deeper into short-term rentals, such as those offered by Airbnb, primarily focusing on interviews with hosts. Simultaneously, we will consider related roles within the platform economy, including cleaning staff and individuals responsible for key management and apartment surveillance.

These three main sectors from which respondents will be selected will be cross-examined with the work on online selling platforms, commonly known as "e-commerce". Frequently, digital platform workers use other platforms, such as e-commerce, to supplement their incomes and ensure sufficient revenue for their reproduction.

The anticipated method for connecting with respondents involves utilizing platforms as clients. This includes taking a trip with Uber Moto, commissioning tasks on Microworker or Appen, and renting short-term accommodation. Once initial contact is established, we consider the use of snowball sampling essential.

Furthermore, compensating respondents for the time dedicated to the interview is considered valuable to obtain a substantial amount of high-quality data. This practice promotes inclusivity by accommodating extremely marginalized workers who may otherwise encounter difficulties in interrupting their remunerated activities. The aim is to encourage greater eloquence from the chosen cases and improve the efficiency of the interview process.

The research team will also immerse themselves in the field through participant observation and ethnographic explorations. By actively engaging with the daily lives of gig workers and local communities, researchers can observe firsthand the informal practices that shape their interactions with digital platforms. This method enables the identification of hidden dynamics and unspoken rules governing the informal aspects of the gig economy. In addition to that, we will explore the possibility of looking at cyberspaces frequented by platform workers – such as social media, chats, blogs, and other digital channels – as another source of retrieving the empirical data, according to what some scholars have defined as “netnography” (Kozinets, 2015).

While the research team has considerable experience of fieldwork in Latin America (all team members speak Brazilian Portuguese), collaboration with local partners will also be essential. Local partners will facilitate access to key informants, provide cultural insights, and help navigate the intricacies of the informal economy within the specific geographical and cultural context of Brazil.

In conclusion, the extended case method and the employment of qualitative techniques allows for a deep examination of the role of informality within the gig economy. By exploring individual and situated cases, the research can uncover the multifaceted ways in which informal practices influence the strategies of gig workers, the policies of platform companies, and the local dynamics of employment. The choice of Brazil, and specifically Rio de Janeiro, as the research site provides a valuable South-to-North perspective. This approach challenges the often Eurocentric views of the gig economy, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of how informality operates in a context shaped by historical heterogeneity, economic disparities, and cultural specificities of the Global South. Finally, rather than simply generalizing the experiences of gig workers, the research team aims to uncover the specificities that distinguish the Brazilian

Annex I

case, contributing to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the global gig economy and its intersection with the dynamics of global informalization.

- Burawoy, M. (1998). The Extended Case Method. *Sociological Theory*, 16(1), 4–33. JSTOR.
- Cardano, M., & Gariglio, L. (A c. Di). (2022). *Metodi qualitativi: Pratiche di ricerca in presenza, a distanza e ibride (1a edizione)*. Carocci editore.
- Eliasoph, N., & Lichterman, P. (1999). «We Begin with Our Favorite Theory...»: Reconstructing the Extended Case Method. *Sociological Theory*, 17(2), 228–234. JSTOR.
- Kozinets, R. V. (2015). *Netnography: Redefined (2nd edition)*. Sage.
- Marzano, M. (2006). *Etnografia e ricerca sociale (1. ed)*. GLF editori Laterza.
- Strauss, A. L., & Corbin, J. M. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Sage Publications.
- Tavory, I., & Timmermans, S. (2009). Two cases of ethnography: Grounded theory and the extended case method. *Ethnography*, 10(3), 243–263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1466138109339042>
- Van Velsen, J. (1979). The Extended-case Method and Situational Analysis. In A. L. Epstein (A c. Di), *The Craft of Social Anthropology* (pp. 129–149). Pergamon. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-023693-3.50011-9>
- Wadham, H., & Warren, R. C. (2014). Telling Organizational Tales: The Extended Case Method in Practice. *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428113513619>

1.3 Quality and composition of the research team (max. 1.000 words)

Please describe the research team highlighting how each member contributes and brings the necessary skills for the project

The research team is structured to provide the DIOIN project with a robust disciplinary foundation and ensure a fruitful collaboration across various departments, with the Télécom department of Institut Polytechnique de Paris serving as the primary partner. This project represents the second phase of a prior collaboration that investigated the platform economy in the global South, resulting in the publication of an article in the French scientific journal "Pouvoirs" in 2023. Therefore, the project builds upon an already established collaboration, further strengthening the foundations of research work and international cooperation among partner departments.

Antonio Casilli, a distinguished researcher and associate professor from the aforementioned department, is internationally recognized as a sociologist specializing in the study of Digital Labour. Additionally, Casilli serves as a researcher at the Interdisciplinary Institute of Innovation, a collaborative research unit of the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS). He is also an associate member of LACI-IIAC (Interdisciplinary Critical Anthropology Laboratory) associated with the School for Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences (EHESS, Paris). Since 2007, he has led the seminar "Studying Digital Cultures". Since 2018, Casilli has held the position of faculty fellow at the Nexa Center for Internet and Society at the Polytechnic University of Turin.

Furthermore, he is a member and founder of the Digital Platform Labour (DiPLab) interdisciplinary research group, a prominent international network dedicated to the study of Digital Labour and the platform economy. DiPLab plays a pivotal role as the organizer of the "International Network on Digital Work" (INDL) conferences, serving as a crucial meeting point for the presentation of advancements in the scientific field.

Casilli's research primarily centers on digital uses, work, and public freedoms. He has conducted numerous international field investigations.

Gianmarco Peterlongo, currently holds the position of research fellow at the Department of Social and Political Sciences of the University of Milan, working within the ERC project CRAFTWORK under the supervision of Professor Alessandro Gandini. The project methodologically pioneers an innovative fusion of digital and qualitative research techniques to explore labor complexities, including participant selection (scraping from social media) and online ethnographic methodologies. Furthermore, he authored a 2023 book exploring the links among informality, technology, and platform work, based on a global ethnography involving ride-hailing workers in Argentina and food delivery workers in Italy. His research interests focus on themes related to the futures of work and forms of employment in contemporary societies, with particular attention to the role of urban informality and the impact of digital technologies, using qualitative and

Annex I

ethnographic methodologies. In recent years, he has conducted several research periods abroad, particularly in EU countries and Latin America. Finally, given the relevance and complexity of ERC projects, Peterlongo's expertise in such kind projects is very helpful in coordinating the team's activities and being aware of the challenges of timing and of research outputs.

Ludmila Costhek Abílio is a senior researcher at the Center for Trade Union Studies and Labor Economics (CESIT) at the University of Campinas (UNICAMP). Her research is dedicated to exploring the concept of the Uberization of labor, with particular attention to "subsunção da viração" (subsumption of "making do"). This concept involves digital platforms capturing the precarious and survival-oriented conditions of the lower strata of the Brazilian working class. This Abílio's concept was introduced by the preceding team and published in French literature as "économie de la débrouille" (economy of resourcefulness). Thus, Abílio's participation ensures the continuity and deepening of the research line. Abílio's work focuses primarily on the study of informal labor and its relation to capitalist accumulation in the Global South. She is currently recognized as one of the key authorities in Brazil on the Uberization of labor. Her participation in the research team is essential to provide expertise based on previous studies on local Brazilian issues and to leverage her competence in the field. In addition, collaboration with CESIT would provide the DIOIN project with an enhanced international perspective and a network of advanced, high-quality research centers in the Global South. This collaboration aims to contribute the insights of Latin American critical sociology, thereby expanding the potential for achieving profoundly innovative results.

Federico De Stavola, serving as the Principal Investigator in this project, currently holds the position of research fellow at the University of Bergamo within the Department of Lettere, Filosofia, e Comunicazione, under the supervision of Professor Marco Marzano. His area of focus centers on the digitalization of labor in Latin America. Presently, his primary commitment is directed towards the publication of a monograph titled "A Sud della piattaforma: lavoro e capitale nelle piattaforme di food delivery a Città del Messico". His international trajectory, culminating in the completion of a Ph.D. in Latin American Studies at the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, enriches the team with a profound understanding of the Latin American sociological discourse and an in-depth knowledge of key dynamics in the subcontinent. Moreover, De Stavola's research theme is based on the self-organization of labor, informalization and digital platform management forms in the Latin American Global South.

In summary, the diverse research team from Italy, Brazil, and France offers a valuable cross-cultural perspective. The collaboration among the mentioned departments provides the DIOIN project access to scientific literature and sociological traditions that often have limited interaction and communication among themselves. Leveraging their collaborative history, the team integrates innovative insights with proven methodologies, enhancing the research process. The prior collaboration among three of the four team members further ensures the efficiency of internal cooperation. The research group, thus composed, provides the University of Bergamo, as the funder, with the expectation of innovative, original, and high-quality results, as well as partnerships with three other significant research centers, not only at the European level but also on a transcontinental scale. Moreover, the opportunity to fund the DIOIN project allows University of Bergamo to advance in a field of research—that of digital work in the Global South (in our case, Latin America)—relatively unexplored at the European level and even less so from a Global South perspective.

2 Project implementation

2.1 Project work plan, including timing, deliverables (max 1.500 words)

Please describe

- *the work plan overall structure, including deliverables and gantt*
- *strategies and plans aimed to reach both results of at least **one joint publication** and the design of a **draft idea for a potential proposal** to be submitted under and Horizon Europe calls for proposal. Please also specify the title and the characteristics of the Journal you intend to have your paper published in (*)*

The project will span a duration of 14 months, from May 2024 to June 2025, divided into four sub-periods:

1. From May 2024 to August 2024: International meetings with the research group and allocation of the literature analysis workload on the topic, in English, Spanish, French, Portuguese, and Italian. The aim is to gather the broadest set of information on the state of the art and emphasize the innovative character of the

Annex I

					<p>fieldwork (1 trip + accommodation for 2 months) and a dissemination moment in Sao Paulo (1 internal trip + accommodation).</p> <p>The fourth (4) period includes three dissemination moments for the presentation of final results, with two outgoing (2 trips + accommodation) and one incoming for both Dr. Casilli and Dr. Abilio (2 trip + accommodation).</p> <p>Provisional total trip and accommodation: 9.</p>
Laboratories, consumables and equipment (i.e. software licences)	€	€890	€	€	<p>Multi-User License Atlas.ti - 5 Users Annually.</p> <p>The license is deemed necessary to be able to share the separately conducted QDA from each team member and collaborate in the cloud on the same material.</p>
Other goods, works and services	€	€	€1000 €1000 €2000	€	<p>The initial budget allocation (€1000, first item) is deemed indispensable for acquiring services, which include rides with UberMoto, tasks on platforms such as Microworker or Appen, and short-term rentals through Airbnb. In accordance with the methodological section, digital applications under the Principal Investigator's name will be employed to procure services, duly invoiced, for the purpose of engaging with workers who will form the respondent sample. This approach facilitates also participant observation as clients. The allocated budget plays a crucial role in establishing initial contacts with workers and recruiting interviewees.</p> <p>Allocating funds for the transcription service (€1000, second item) is considered imperative to expedite the project timeline and ensure the production of high-quality results within a reasonable timeframe. This expense is viewed as a strategic investment, propelling the project significantly forward in terms of saturating the research field with comprehensive data.</p> <p>The third item (€2000), falling under the case specified in Article 4, paragraph 4 (“beni e servizi strettamente necessari allo sviluppo dell’attività di ricerca collaborativa”), pertains to the remuneration for consultancy services disbursed throughout the one-year duration of the DIOIN project. These services are provided by the Department of Social and Political Sciences of the University of Milan and the ERC project CRAFTWORK, with which a collaborative engagement has been established. This consultancy is deemed essential for advancing the fieldwork and drafting the European project. The Department's expertise</p>

Annex I

					in ethnographic research, where it holds a pioneering role in Italy in the innovative fusion of digital methodologies and qualitative research (including scraping from social media and online ethnographic methodologies), coupled with its leadership of an ERC project, highlights its competence in the specific domains of European project design and ethnographic research.
Access to research infrastructure	€	€	€	€	
Project total costs	€600	€2890	€7500	€4000	€14.990
Requested grant	€600	€2890	€7500	€4000	€14.990

Additional funding

Please fill in the table below and provide a description and full justification of the amount of the additional requested funding. Please be aware that this extra funding is subjected to the approval and to the availability of funds.

Please consider being able to reach your main goals even without this amount.

Cost Category	Months M1-M6	Months M7-Mxx	Total (M1-Mxx)	Justification of items and the needed of extra funds
Travel and subsistence	€	€	€	
Laboratories consumables and equipment (software licences)	€	€	€	
Other goods, works and services	€	€	€	
Access to research infrastructure	€	€	€	
Project total costs	€	€	€	
Requested grant	€	€	€	

(* please be aware that Authors from University of Bergamo, that is affiliated with the Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane (CRUI), may publish open access in some journals listed [here](#), at no charge to the author.

Annex I

Antonio Casilli

Citizenship: Italian - **Country of residence:** France

E-mail: antonio.casilli@ip-paris.fr

Current Positions

2019-- - **Full Professor**, sociology, Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris), Telecommunications engineering school (Telecom Paris), department of Economic and Social Sciences, FR.

2015-- - **Member**, Interdisciplinary Institute on Innovation (i3), CNRS, FR.

2023-24 - **Visiting professor**, Centre for Internet and Society (CIS), CNRS, FR.

Current Professional Memberships

2021-- - **Member of the Scholarly Council**, Center for Critical Internet Inquiry (C2i2), UCLA, US.

2021-- - **Associate Researcher**, Weizenbaum-Institut, Criticality of AI Systems group, Berlin, DE.

2017-- - **Faculty Fellow**, Nexa Center Internet & Society, Polytechnic University of Turin, IT.

2008-- - **Associate Researcher**, School for Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences (EHESS), Laboratory for Interdisciplinary Critical Anthropology - Interdisciplinary Institute on Contemporary Anthropology, LACI-IIAC, Paris, FR.

Education

2018 - **HDR (Accreditation to Supervise Research)**, Sociology, University Paris Dauphine, FR.

2006 - **PhD**, Sociology, EHESS, Paris, FR.

1997 - **Master**, Sociology "Firms and Deviance", University Luigi Bocconi, Milan, IT.

1996 - **Laurea**, Economics, Bocconi University, Milan, IT.

Professional History

2011-19 - **Associate Professor (tenured)**, Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris), Telecommunications engineering school (Telecom Paris), department of Economic and Social Sciences.

2010-11 - **Research Scientist**, EHESS, Edgar Morin Centre, Paris, FR.

2007-08 - **Research Scientist**, Nestlé Research Centre, Lausanne, CH.

2002-09 - **Adjunct Lecturer**, Paris 13/IMT Business School, Bobigny/Evry, FR.

1999-02 - **Editor**, DeriveApprodi Editore, Rome, IT.

1999-00 - **Research Assistant**, Political Economy Institute, Bocconi University, Milan, IT

1998-00 - **Freelance Multimedia Designer**, Milan, IT.

PUBLICATIONS

I have authored 5 monographs, co-authored 3 volumes, edited 4 journal issues, authored or co-authored 88 peer-reviewed articles and book chapters (h-index 30). My books and articles have been translated in 8 languages.

Books

- (2019). [Waiting for the Robots. An Inquiry Into Digital Labor] *En attendant les robots. Enquête sur le travail du clic*. Éditions du Seuil.
[transl. Eng.] [Forthcoming 2024] *Waiting for the Robots*, U. of Chicago Press.
[transl. Greek] [Forthcoming 2024] *Περιμένοντας τα ρομπότ*, Ropi Ekdoseis.
[transl. Spanish] (2022) *Esperando a los robots*, LOM. El-Maraya. في انتظار الروبوت
2022) *الروبوت* Ar.] [transl.
[transl. Spanish] (2021) *Esperando a los robots*, Punto de Vista. [transl.
Italian] (2020) *Schiavi del clic*, Feltrinelli.
- (2018). [Work, Knowledge, and Surveillance. 5 Essays on Technology] *Trabajo, conocimiento y vigilancia. 5 ensayos sobre tecnología*. Editorial del Estado.
- (2016). [The "pro-ana" phenomenon. Eating disorders and social networks] *Le phénomène "pro-ana". Troubles alimentaires et réseaux sociaux*. Presses des Mines (with Paola Tubaro).
- (2015). [What is digital labor?] *Qu'est-ce que le digital labor?*. Editions de l'INA (with Dominique Cardon).
- (2014). *Against the hypothesis of the "end of privacy". An agent-based modelling approach to social media*. Springer (with Paola Tubaro & Yasaman Sarabi).
- (2010). [Digital relationships: towards a new sociability?] *Les Liaisons numériques: vers une nouvelle sociabilité?*. Editions du Seuil.
- (2000). [Stop Mobbing. Resisting workplace bullying] *Stop mobbing. Resistere alla violenza psicologica sul luogo di lavoro*. DeriveApprodi.
- (1997). [The libertine factory. De Sade and the industrial system] *La Fabbrica libertina. De Sade e il sistema industriale*. Manifesto Libri.

Annex I

Gianmarco Peterlongo

Citizenship: Italian - **Country of residence:** Italy

E-mail: gianmarco.peterlongo@unimi.it

Current Positions

2022-- - Postdoc researcher, sociology, University of Milan, Department of Social & Political Sciences.

Education

2022 - **PhD**, Sociology & Social Research, University of Bologna, IT.

2018 - **Master**, Sociology and Social Research, University of Turin, IT.

2014 - **Laurea triennale**, Sociology, University of Milan-Bicocca, IT.

Other Education

06/2023 Summer School on the Future of Politics and Technology – Speculating at the end (?) of times. University of Napoli Federico II (Italy). 15-18 June 2023.

07/2021 Lucerne PhD Master Class 2021 (prof. Marion Fourcade): On the political economy of digitality. University of Luzern (Switzerland). 23-28 July 2021.

01/2021 Marie Jahoda Winter School of Sociology, Research and Activism. University of Wien (Austria). 25-28 January 2021.

09/2019 Summer School on Social Research and Methods "Paideia", Designing an investigation. Research design from theory to field. Salerno (Italy), 2-6 September 2019.

08/2019 PhD Summer School - European Sociological Association (ESA). Europe and Beyond: Boundaries, Barriers and Belonging. Manchester Univ. (England), 17-20 August 2019.

Research Experiences Abroad

10/2022 – 12/2023 Fieldwork for the Craftwork research project in EU27 countries: Greece (Athens), Germany (Berlin), Portugal (Lisbon and Algarve), Spain (Barcelona).

01/2020 – 04/2020 (Buenos Aires, Argentina) PhD Visiting. IDAES, University of San Martín, Buenos Aires. Supervisor: prof. Veronica Gago (UNSAM).

10/2016 – 01/2017 (Mexico City, Mexico). Master Thesis Abroad Fellowship, University of Turin. Supervisor: prof. Giovanni Semi (University of Turin).

06/2015 – 01/2016 (Mexico City, Mexico). Uni.Coo Research & Cooperation Fellowship, University of Turin. Supervisor: prof. Carlo Genova (Unito) & prof. Héctor Castillo (UNAM).

PUBLICATIONS

2024 - Peterlongo, G. "I verbali segreti del lavoro di piattaforma: lavoro umano e riappropriazione di infrastrutture", in: Borghi, V. e Leonardi, E. (a cura di), *Il sociale messo in forma. Le infrastrutture come cose, processi e logiche della vita collettiva*, Orthotes Editrice (forthcoming).

2023 - Peterlongo, G. "Unpacking informality in the gig-economy". *Sociologia del Lavoro*. 167/2023. (forthcoming)

2023 - Peterlongo, G. & Borghi, V. "Hybridisation of work and the platform informal revolution". *Rassegna Italiana di Sociologia*. 2/2023: 317-344. DOI: 10.1423/107862

2023 - Peterlongo, G. "Imbrigliamento e rifeudalizzazione nella gig-economy. Una ricerca sul caporalato digitale". *Cartografie Sociali*, 15: 115-134.

2023 - Peterlongo, G. *Nella trama dell'algoritmo. Lavoro e circuiti informali nella gig-economy*. Torino: Rosenberg & Sellier. ISBN: 9791259931917

2023 - Peterlongo, G., Marrone, M. & Pirina, G. "Beyond the myths of digitalization: labor, space, and ecology in the digital age", in: Tagliaventi, M. R. e Carbonara, E. (a cura di), *SMEs in the Digital Era: Opportunities and Challenges of the Digital Single Market*, Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 84-103. ISBN: 9781803921631

2023 - Peterlongo, G., Casilli, A., Torres-Cierpe, J. & De Stavola, F. "Des GAFAM aux RUM: plateformes et débrouille dans le Sud global". *Pouvoirs*, 185/2: 51-67. DOI: 10.3917/pouv.185.0051

2021 - Peterlongo, G., Pirina, G. & Marrone, M., "La classe operaia va nel cyberspazio. Il capitalismo di piattaforma oltre i miti della digitalizzazione". *Economia e Società Regionale*, 2/2021: 127-151. DOI: 10.3280/ES2021-001011

2020 - Peterlongo, G. & Marrone, M., "Where Platforms Meet Infrastructures: Digital Platforms, Urban Resistance and the Ambivalence of the City in the Italian Case of Bologna". *Work Organisation, Labor & Globalisation*, 1/14: 119-135. DOI: 10.13169/workorglaboglob.14.1.0119

2020 - Peterlongo, G., "Sulle Frontiere del capitale: la disputa per i mercati a Città del Messico". In: AA.VV., *Logistica e America Latina, Quaderni di Into the Black Box*, University of Bologna, pp. 147-174. ISBN 9788854970267, DOI: 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/6434

2018 - Peterlongo, G., "Franeleros: trasformazione urbana e lavoro informale a Città del Messico" *América Crítica Journal*. 1/2: 95-116. DOI: 10.13125/americacritica/3016

Annex I

Ludmila Costhek Abílio

Nationality: Brazilian

Rua do Sol, 148, Casa 141, Campinas – São Paulo – Brasil – 13085-260

Email: l.c.abilio@gmail.com ▪ Tel: + 55 11991437554

CURRENT POSTS HELD

Visiting Professor, Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Campinas

Researcher, Institute of Advanced Studies, University of São Paulo

EDUCATION

PhD in Social Sciences, University of Campinas (UNICAMP), Brazil, 2007-2011

MPhil in Sociology, University of Sao Paulo (USP), Brazil, 2003-2005

BSc in Social Sciences, University of Sao Paulo (USP), Brazil, 1997-2001

AWARDS AND FUNDING (of the last 3 years)

- 2023** Co-I. Formalization of precarity. *Data and Society*, NY Funder: D&S.
- 2022-ongoing** PI. Health and work conditions of delivery workers. University of Campinas. Funder: Labour prosecutors office (MPT).
- 2021-2022** PI. Uberization: Conditions of work and health of the just-in-time worker. CESIT/UNICAMP. Funder: Labour prosecutors office (MPT).
- 2021** PI. Digitalization and the future of work in the pharmaceutical industry in Brazil. International Labour Organization (ILO).
- 2021** PI. Digital platforms, legal reconfigurations, and new rights. Universidade Federal do Paraná/ MPT.
- 2021 - ongoing** Co-I. Grey zones and Territory: Transformation of work and the emerging figure of Platform Worker. A France-Brazil comparison. ANR-FAPESP.
- 2019-2022** Co-I. Latwork. Developing research and innovation capacities of Latin American HEI for the analysis of the informal labour market. Lead institution: Universidad Viña del Mar, Chile. Erasmus program/European Commission.

PUBLICATIONS Peer-reviewed articles and Chapters of Books (most relevant 10 out of 62)

Google Scholar Citations on December 2023: 2,440

ABÍLIO, L. Uberization: the periphery as the future of work? In: HUWS, U.; ADITI, S. *Platformization and Informality*. Palgrave Macmillan (forthcoming).

ABÍLIO, L. Brazil: Inequalities, labour exploitation and new informalization processes. In: Atzeni, M.; Mezzadri, a.; Azzellini, D.; Moore, p.; Apitzsch, u. *Research Handbook on the Global Political Economy of Work*. Ed Edward Elgar (forthcoming).

Abilio, L., Grohmann, R., Weiss, H. Struggles of delivery workers in Brazil: working conditions and collective organisation during the pandemic. *Journal of labor and society*. 2021 p.1-19 doi:10.1163/24714607-bja10012

ABÍLIO, L. Uberization: the just-in-time worker era? *Revista Estudos Avançados*, vol. 34, n.28, p.111-126, jan/abr 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0103-4014.2020.3498.008>

Manzano, M.; Krein, D.; **Abilio, L.** The dynamics of labour informality in Brazil, 2003-2019. *Global labour journal*, 2021, 12(3), p 227-243. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.15173/glj.v12i3.4434>

KISS, L.; FOTHERNINGHAME, D.; KYEGOMBE, N.; MCALPINE, A.; **ABÍLIO, L.C.**; KYAMULAB, A.; WALAKIRA, E.; DEVIRES, K.; TANTON, C. Violence, abuse and exploitation among trafficked women and girls: a mixed-methods study in Nigeria and Uganda. *BMC Public Health*.

GROHMANN, R.; PEREIRA, G.; GUERRA, A. **ABÍLIO, L.C.**; MORESCHI, B.; JURNO, A. Platform scams: Brazilian workers experiences of dishonest and uncertain algorithmic management. *New Media and Society*. Vol. 24, n.07, pp. 1611–1631, 2022.

ABÍLIO, L. . Digital platforms and uberization: towards the globalization of an administrated south? *Contracampo*, Niterói, v. 39, n. 1, p. 12-26, abr./jul. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.22409/contracampo.v39i1> Avaliable at https://periodicos.uff.br/contracampo/article/view/38579/html_en

ABÍLIO, L. Uberização: do empreendedorismo para o autogerenciamento subordinado. [Uberisation: From entrepreneurship to subordinated management]. *Revista Psicoperspectivas: Individuo y sociedad*. Vol, 18, n.03, p.1-11, 2019. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5027/psicoperspectivas-vol18-issue3-fulltext-1674>

GRIGERA, J. WEBBER, J. (editors). **ABÍLIO, L.**; ANTUNES, R.; FERNANDES, S.; MATTOS, M.; NUNES, R.; PAULANI, L.; PURDY, S. *The long Brazilian crisis: A forum*. *Historical Materialism*. Vol 27, n. 02, 2019.

Annex I

Federico De Stavola

Nationality: italian

Country of residence: Italy

Email: federico.destavola@unibg.it - **Telephone number:** +393890792261

Current position:

Inizio Assegno di Ricerca all'Università di Bergamo nel dipartimento di Lettere, Filosofia, Comunicazione sotto la supervisione del Prof. Marco Marzano.

Settore disciplinare: SPS/09 Sociologia dei processi economici e del lavoro

Education:

2018 - 2022

PhD in Latin American Studies, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, UNAM, Mexico.

With a visiting period at the Escuela Interdisciplinaria de Altos Estudios Sociales (IDAES), Universidad Nacional de San Martín, Buenos Aires, Argentina.

Dissertation Title: "Al Sur de la plataforma: trabajo y capital en la app latinoamericana Rappi."

2013 - 2016

Master's Degree in Local and Global Development

Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna, Italy.

Including participation in the Overseas university exchange program at the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. Recipient of the research scholarship for thesis abroad.

Thesis Title: "Il lavoro nella fabbrica globalizzata: regime produttivo, conflitto e soggettività nella maquila di Monclova, Messico."

2008 - 2012

Bachelor's Degree in Sociology and Social Research

University of Florence, Italy.

Thesis Title: "Spazio-tempo nel capitalismo. Le tendenze storico-geografiche attraverso i contributi di David Harvey e Giovanni Arrighi."

Publications:

De Stavola F., (2024 - forthcoming). Reseña de "IIRSA: entre integración regional y racionalidad logística", Alessandro Peregalli (Peter Lang, 2022). De Raíz diversa: revista especializada en Estudios Latinoamericanos.

De Stavola F., (2024 - forthcoming). El trabajo de plataforma en la heterogeneidad latinoamericana: las plataformas de entrega de comida en Ciudad de México entre subsunción del apañe y dispositivos de gestión, in Trabajo platformizado en América Latina, COLMEX.

Casilli, A. A., Torres-Cierpe, J., De Stavola, F., & Peterlongo, G. (2023). Des GAFAM aux RUM: plateformes et débrouille dans le Sud global. Pouvoirs, (2), 51-67.

De Stavola F., (2023). Reseña de "IIRSA: entre integración regional y racionalidad logística", Alessandro Peregalli (Peter Lang, 2022). De Raíz diversa: revista especializada en Estudios Latinoamericanos.

De Stavola F., (2023). El trabajo de plataforma en la heterogeneidad latinoamericana: las plataformas de entrega de comida en Ciudad de México entre subsunción del apañe y dispositivos de gestión, in Trabajo platformizado en América Latina, COLMEX.

De Stavola F., (2023). Plataformas, repartidores y América Latina: Rappi en México. in: Pirone, Maurilio; Cuppini, Niccolò; Frapporti, Mattia; Benvegnù, Carlotta; Milesi, Floriano. (Org.). Logistica y America Latina. 2ed. latinoamericana: Dipartimento delle arti di Bologna y CLACSO.

De Stavola F., (2021). El smartphone de Foucault. Poder, trabajo y subjetividad en las plataformas digitales de entrega a domicilio: el análisis de la app latinoamericana Rappi. Arxius revista de sociologia, N°44, pp. 49- 64.

De Stavola, F., (2020). Potere, controllo e soggettività nelle piattaforme digitali di food delivery: un'analisi foucaultiana dell'app latinoamericana Rappi. Sociologia del Lavoro, 158, 178-198. <https://doi.org/10.3280/SL2020-158009>.

Ambroggi, C.; De Stavola, F.; Peregalli, Alessandro; Peterlongo, G., (2020). Introduzione. In: Pirone, Maurilio; Cuppini, Niccolò; Frapporti, Mattia; Benvegnù, Carlotta; Milesi, Floriano. (Org.). Logistica e America Latina. 1ed. Bologna: Dipartimento delle Arti, 2020, v. , p. 7-20.

De Stavola F., (2020), Piattaforme, riders e America Latina: Rappi in Messico in: Pirone, Maurilio; Cuppini, Niccolò; Frapporti, Mattia; Benvegnù, Carlotta; Milesi, Floriano. (Org.). Logistica e America Latina. 1ed. Bologna: Dipartimento delle Arti, 2020, v. , p. 7-20.